

Exploration of Data Coding Methods in Wireless Computer Networks

A.V. Potebnia, S.D. Pogorilyy

The comparative analysis of Forward Error Correction methods in IEEE 802.11a/b/g computer networks has been performed. The mathematical model of wireless communication channel, which takes into account the signal propagation in the environment, has been suggested. A class of convolutional codes has been investigated, and its significant corrective potential has been determined. A number of drawbacks of existing protocols have been identified, and recommendations for their elimination have been prepared.

Keywords: data coding methods, IEEE 802.11a/b/g standards, convolutional coding, CCK, PBCC, barker sequences, forward error correction, constellation diagram, combinatorial optimization problem, Viterbi decoder, wireless networks.

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Introduction

Wireless computer systems are very wide-spread in telecommunications, and their number is growing exponentially over the past decades. The users are attracted by a simple setting procedure of such networks, high mobility of devices, recognition and support of basic standards by the manufacturers [1]. As a result, the WWRF (*Wireless World Research Forum*) experts predict that the total number of wireless devices will reach 7 trillion by 2020 [2].

However, the usage of such networks has several drawbacks, which include significant energy consumption, lower data transmission rate compared to the wired systems and the presence of significant problems with security. There are ongoing intensive researches related to the development of new protocols to eliminate these drawbacks. For example, the IEEE library now contains 547 wireless communication standards, 137 of which are at the stage of *Active Unapproved Draft*.

One of the critical drawbacks of the wireless networks is their poor resistance to external interference, which results in a significant reduction of the transmission rate. Thus, an important area of research is the development of the noise-immune codes that reduce the necessary signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and provide the increasing of the coding gain (CG), each decibel of which is assessed in the millions of dollars. The usage of the reliable codes is required for the minimization of the antenna size,

decreasing of the transmitters power and enhancing of the coverage and operating speed of the wireless networks. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to study *the Forward Error Correction* methods used in the current protocols and to provide the recommendations for their improvement in the new generation systems.

Mathematical Model of the Communication Channel in the Wireless Systems

Mathematical models taking into account the peculiarities of radio wave propagation in the surrounding are widely used to describe the information channels. In particular, it is necessary to consider the phenomenon of inter-symbol interference related to the formation of the received signal as a superposition of numerous initial signals with different delay time [3].

Significant distortion of the received signal is also caused by the limitation of channel frequency bandwidth, resulting in the exclusion of frequency components whose values are not included in the selected range. Thus, the formation of more compact spectrum is combined with smoothing of signal fronts, overlapping of adjacent pulses and their corruption.

With respect to these restrictions, the wireless network standards provide special methods for compensation of inter-symbol interference. For example, the resistance of OFDM (*Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing*) radio signal to multipath wave propagation is ensured by the introduction of a guard interval τ_g [4]. Moreover, its value is determined by the typical delay of the radio signal, and according to the IEEE 802.11a/g standards, oriented at application in the indoor conditions, equals to $0.4 - 0.8 \mu\text{s}$ [5].

However, in the outdoor environment such devices retain efficiency only at presence of the direct visibility and fully open Fresnel zone. Even its partial closure with obstacles leads to the destruction of data packages and rapid degradation of the communication channel. A classic example that confirms the inability of Wi-Fi devices to counteract the adverse impact of the reflected signals is the instability of the connections established over the water surface.

Per contra, in the IEEE 802.16 WiMax systems designed for ensuring of considerable coverage, the interval τ_g is set by a *Cyclic Prefix* (CP) as the ratio to the total duration of the pulse. The maximum possible value $CP = 1/4$ provides the effective suppression of inter-symbol interference in the dense urban environment, while the low values $CP = 1/32$ are used in the absence of obstacles to the signal propagation. It should be noted that the ability of WiMax devices to set higher τ_g values is realized by means of large pulse duration, which is hundreds of times greater than in IEEE 802.11a/g systems. Thus, the requirements for high-speed response are met by the allocation of the additional OFDM flows (256 and more in total) [6].

Suppose the digital communication channel is discrete in time, i.e. its input $u(k)$ and output $r(k)$ signals are accessible for observation and processing only at the fixed moments of time. Inter-symbol distortions lead to the appearance of a

memory in the channel, which determines the dependence of the error probability in any symbol as a function of the previously transmitted bits.

Let the capacity of channel memory is equal to $L + 1$, and the receiver signal formation involves the current symbol and L of previous bits coming from the reflected waves. The mathematical model of channel based on the following considerations is given in Figure 1. It looks like a finite impulse response filter of order L presented

Figure 1. Discrete-time model of the communication channel with finite memory and additive Gaussian noise

by a set of delay blocks Z^{-1} and corresponding filtration coefficients h_k . Due to the existing restrictions $h(k) = 0$ at $k < 0$ and $k > L$. Since the transmitter sends the symbols in the discrete moments of time with rate $1/T$, the total time interval, which extends the impact of one bit, reaches LT seconds.

Thus, the output signal $r(k)$ is generated by the convolution of the input signal $u(k) = \sum_i u_i \delta(k - i)$ and the channel transmission function $h(k)$. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the background noise effect of the transmission system. In the above model, the impact of noise is represented by adding the white Gaussian noise with the uniform spectrum, variance σ^2 and zero mean value to the useful signal. Therefore, the expression for the receiver signal takes the following form:

$$r(k) = \sum_i u_i h(k - i) + n(k).$$

The developed model with discrete time and white noise is used in this paper to describe high speed transmission in the wireless channel with the limited frequency band.

Convolutional Data Coding

Information sequence $u = \langle u_0, u_1, \dots, u_{n-1} \rangle$ of discrete binary symbols $u_k \in \{0, 1\}, k = 0, 1, \dots$ must be encoded before entering the communication channel to eliminate distortions related to the adverse influence of noise and interference. Currently, there are two types of *Forward Error Correction* (FEC): block coding and convolutional coding [7]. In the first case, the information sequence is divided into blocks $u = \langle u_0, u_1, \dots, u_{K-1} \rangle$ of dimensionality K , which are called messages. At the next stage, the transmitter shall assign to each message u the corresponding N -length sequence of code symbols $v = \langle v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{N-1} \rangle$, which is called a code word. In addition to useful information, the created word contains redundant service data.

The set of 2^K code words is called (N, K) block code, and the ratio $R = K/N$ – its rate. For example, DVB-S2 satellite television (digital video broadcasting) involves a combination of block codes with different values $R = 1/2, 2/3, 3/4, 5/6, 7/8, \dots$ and the corresponding requirements for the quality of the resulting signal [8].

In case of convolutional coding, the transmitter shall distribute the sequence u into sub-blocks $u_n = (u_n^{(1)}, u_n^{(2)}, \dots, u_n^{(d)})$ of d symbols. Further the resulting set is reflected in the code sequence v of dimensionality c , composed of sub-blocks $v_n = (v_n^{(1)}, v_n^{(2)}, \dots, v_n^{(c)})$, $n = 0, 1, \dots$

Thus, the sub-block v_n is determined not only by the relevant information set u_n , but also by the previous sub-blocks $u_{n-1}, u_{n-2}, \dots, u_{n-m}$, where m is the capacity of transmitter memory. The set of all possible code sequences forms a convolutional code C , and the ratio $R = d/c$ is called its rate. Convolutional code is used in the wireless IEEE 802.16a WiMax devices and IEEE 802.11a/b/g Wi-Fi systems.

Figure 2 shows an example of the device, capable to form the convolutional noise-immune code. In its architecture the

Figure 2. Example of the convolution coding device

input sequence of information symbols goes to the shift register represented as m

memory cells. The device generates two output sequences $v^{(1)} = \langle v_0^{(1)}, v_1^{(1)}, \dots \rangle$ and $v^{(2)} = \langle v_0^{(2)}, v_1^{(2)}, \dots \rangle$ which after interleaving are converted into result code $\langle v_0^{(1)}, v_0^{(2)}, v_1^{(1)}, v_1^{(2)} \dots \rangle$ that is sent to the channel.

In this case, two bits at the output correspond to each input information symbol, i.e. coding rate $R = 1/2$. To describe the device memory, we shall introduce the concept of the state $\sigma_t = u_{t-1}u_{t-2}$, which is determined by the current content of the shift register, and has a decisive influence on the formation of the output signals. The convolution coding procedure can be represented using the state chart similar to De Bruijn graph.

An example of the state chart for the considered convolutional encoder is given in Figure 3. In this case, the device contains only one binary input, so indegrees and outdegrees of the corresponding graph's nodes are equal to two. Receiving of each next bit is accompanied by the transition of the system to a new state with the generation of two code symbols. The signal coding procedure can be represented by the deployment of the state chart in time. For example, in the case of zero initial system's state $\sigma_0 = 00$, the input information sequence 1110 should be transformed into 11 01 10 01 output code.

Figure 3. Example of the encoder state chart

The usage of trellis diagrams is very common for representing all permitted paths, through which the encoder can move at data processing. In such trellis, nodes shall be the states of the system for each coding phase, while edges are possible directions of transitions between them. Any information sequence at the encoder input has the corresponding unique path in the trellis with the appropriate set of output symbols. An example of the trellis for encoder given in this paper is shown in Figure 4. In this diagram, the upper and lower edges emanating from each node correspond to input symbols 0 and 1.

Unlike radio environment, where a separate broadcasting range is allotted for each transmitter, in the wireless networks, the organization of coexistence of multiple users in a single frequency band is important. Therefore, all 802.11 family of protocols is based on the spread spectrum technology, according to which the initial signal must be distributed

over the frequency band. For example, in the DSSS (*Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum*) technology, each information bit is replaced with noise-like code of length n , which leads to the expansion of the signal spectrum by n times and the corresponding decrease in its amplitude. Only the target receiver can distinguish such signal from the total noise through its multiplying by the used code sequence and calculating

the autocorrelation function.

The DSSS method is used in the basic IEEE 802.11 protocol to ensure the transmission speed of 1 or 2 Mbit/s. In this case, the “1” symbols are presented by Barker sequences of 11100010010 bits, while zeros are encoded by inverted sets.

To ensure higher transmission speed the IEEE 802.11b standard, instead of Barker sets, uses the complementary codes defined in the complex space (*Complementary Code Keying* (CCK) technology) [9]. With the speed of 11 Mbit/s, the coding procedure involves distribution of the input sequence into the sets of 8 symbols. Elements of the complementary code are represented by the numbers $c_i = e^{j\theta_k}$, where θ_k depend on the values of four phases $\{\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3, \phi_4\}$:

$$[\theta_0 \ \theta_1 \ \theta_2 \ \theta_3 \ \theta_4 \ \theta_5 \ \theta_6 \ \theta_7] = F \times \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \\ \phi_3 \\ \phi_4 \end{bmatrix},$$

where F is a forming matrix. Values ϕ_i are set by the i -th pair of the input sequence bits. Each element c_i acquires one of the 8 values θ_k and the total number of possible codes is quite large. As a result, one transmitted symbol may contain several encoded bits, which is a key factor to speed up their transmission.

Figure 4. Example of the encoder trellis diagram

the current and six previous bits stored in memory cells. Therefore, each input symbol d is replaced by the two coded bits (c_0, c_1) , and the coding rate is equal to $r = 1/2$. With the speed of 11 Mbit/s, the output bits define one symbol of the four-position QPSK-modulation. The low-speed mode of 5.5 Mbit/s is implemented by virtue of the two-position BPSK-modulation and sequential transmission of bits c_0 and c_1 .

However, the distribution of generated symbols in the phase space is also essential for reducing decoding errors. From this perspective, the usage of complementary codes is not optimal, and consequently IEEE 802.11b standard additionally applies *Packet Binary Convolutional Coding* (PBCC). The speed levels of 5.5, 11 and 22 Mbit/s are ensured by means of this technology [10].

In this case, the stream of information bits goes to the six-bit shift register, whose triggers are storing zero values at the initial time (Figure 5). Output bits of the encoder are determined by the exclusive OR operations over the values of

Figure 5. Scheme of the convolutional encoder in accordance with the IEEE 802.11b standard

A constellation diagram is a geometrical reflection of the signal states set. For example, the QPSK-modulation envisages four discrete states 00, 01, 10 and 11, and each of them has the corresponding value of the generated signal phase (Figure 6). In contrast to this technique, the capacities of the BPSK-modulation are limited to the transmission of a single code bit (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Possible types of the signal constellations for the convolutional coding

Figure 7. Possible types of the signal constellations for the convolutional coding

When applying the method of convolutional coding, it is necessary to distribute the generated signal over the full bandwidth of 22 MHz. For this purpose, the PBCC technology uses a special method for variation of the QPSK and BPSK constellation diagrams. Choice of the constellation instance is defined by the control signal S , represented as a pseudorandom sequence with a repetition period of 256 bits. This sequence is formed by cyclic shift of the first three bits of the initial vector 0011001110001011, which contains the equal numbers of zeros and ones. It should be noted that the IEEE 802.11g standard is an improved version of its predecessor and uses the same methods of data coding with advanced modulation schemes [11]. The convolutional codes are also used in many high-speed modes of the IEEE 802.11a protocol [4] as shown in Table 1. The data transmission mode at the speed of 22

Table 1. Parameters of the convolutional codes in accordance with the IEEE 802.11a standard

The data transmission speed, Mbit/s	The modulation scheme	The rate of code r	The number of code bits in the channel	The number of code bits in the OFDM-symbol	The number of data bits in the OFDM-symbol
6	BPSK	1/2	1	48	24
9	BPSK	3/4	1	48	36
12	QPSK	1/2	2	96	48
18	QPSK	3/4	2	96	72
24	16-QAM	1/2	4	192	96
36	16-QAM	3/4	4	192	144
48	64-QAM	2/3	6	288	192
54	64-QAM	3/4	6	288	216

Mbit/s is defined by the IEEE 802.11b+ appendix to the base protocol developed by *Texas Instruments* and supported by many manufacturers. In this case, the encoder scheme is complicated (Figure 8), and its speed increases to $r = 2/3$. In addition, the code bits $c_0 - c_2$ determine one symbol in the 8-position 8-PSK modulation.

The six-bit shift register that is used at the speed modes of 11 and 5.5 Mbit/s has 64 possible states. Therefore, at the modulation stage information bits are located in the phase space much further apart from each other than when using complementary codes. As a result, the convolutional coding provides higher data transmission rate, but its main drawback is the complexity of the hardware implementation. Thus, the development of the efficient methods for the convolutional decoding is a key to a significant improvement of the wireless LAN parameters.

Figure 8. Scheme of the convolutional encoder for data transmission with the enhanced speed (in accordance with the IEEE 802.11b+ protocol)

Structural Properties of the Convolutional Code

The quality of the convolutional code is largely determined by its distance properties. In particular, the free distance of the code is defined as the smallest Hamming distance between its words, i.e.

$$d_{free} = \min_{v \neq v'} \{d_H(v, v')\}.$$

The free distance value determines the corrective properties of the convolutional code. The code C is able to correct a set of error combinations ϵ_t , the number of which does not exceed t , only if $d_{free} > 2t$.

Assume $n_{d_{free}+i}$ is the number of paths in the trellis with weight $d_{free} + i$ that leave the zero state $\sigma_0 = 00$ and return to it only in the end of the route. The value $n_{d_{free}+i}$ is called the $(i + 1)$ -th spectral component of the code, and the sequence $n_{d_{free}+i}, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ is its weight spectrum. The function of the spectrum generation

$$T(W) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} n_{d_{free}+i} W^{d_{free}+i}$$

is called the path weight enumerator.

For example, in the encoder state chart shown in Figure 3, we find all paths that begin and end in the zero state and do not include additional returns to it. By dividing the zero state into two nodes and denoting the edges with symbols

$W^0 = 1$, W and W^2 , where the degree value corresponds to the number of “1”s in the generated code, we get the signal flowchart of the device (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Signal flowchart of the encoder

By defining the formal variables x_1 , x_2 , x_3 to represent the weight of all the paths, which are entering the corresponding intermediate states 10, 11 and 01, we have the next set of expressions:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = x_3 + W^2 \\ x_2 = Wx_1 + Wx_2 \\ x_3 = Wx_1 + Wx_2 \\ T(W) = W^2x_3 \end{cases}$$

Having found from this system of equations the expression for the variable $x_3 = W^3/(1 - 2W)$, we get the function of path weight enumerator $T(W) = W^5/(1 - 2W)$. By analyzing its form, we can define that the free distance of this code is $d_{free} = 5$, and its corrective properties are limited to restoration of two bits. Table 2 shows the values of d_{free}

and the first ten spectral components for the three modes of the convolutional coding used in the IEEE 802.11a standard [12].

Table 2. Corrective properties of the IEEE 802.11a convolutional codes

The rate of code r	The data transmission speed, Mbit/s	The free distance d_{free}	The first ten spectral components
1/2	6, 12, 24	10	11, 0, 38, 0, 193, 0, 1331, 0, 7275, 0
3/4	9, 18, 36, 54	5	8, 31, 160, 892, 4512, 23307, 121077, 625059, 3234886, 16753077
2/3	48	6	1, 16, 48, 158, 642, 2435, 9174, 34705, 131585, 499608

Decoding of the Convolutional Signal

The decoder is aimed to produce the restored signal \bar{u} based on the received information r considering its distortion at the transmission in the channel. It should be noted that in a pure theoretical case, sequences v generated by the convolutional

transmitter are endless. However, in practice they are reduced to sets of limited dimensionality n by introducing tails designed to switch the encoder to its initial state σ_0 (tailbiting).

The decoding process requires the evaluation of the code word \bar{v} for each sequence r . Thus, the decoding error occurs if $\bar{v} \neq v$, where v is the signal generated by the transmitter. The decoder selects the vector $\bar{v} = v$, which increases the probability $p(r|v)$ based on the principle of the maximum-likelihood. In the presence of the channel memory, the decoding procedure for the sequences of great dimensionality can be represented by the maximization problem of the following scalar function:

$$J = - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left(r_k - \sum_{i=0}^L h_i v_{k-i} \right)^2 .$$

Without the minus sign, this cost function is the sum of quadratic deviations between the resulting sets r and the output sequences of the transmitter v . In this case, the choice of the optimal set is a combinatorial optimization problem (COP) and requires the calculation of the J value for all possible code sequences $v = \langle v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{n-1} \rangle$ [13]. The complexity of the decoding procedure is equal to M^n , where M is the number of possible encoder output symbols, $v_k \in \{\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{M-1}\}$, and n is the total message length [14].

In the data transmission systems, the values of n and M can be very large, making it impossible to use the straightforward enumeration of all possible codes v due to the combinatorial explosion phenomenon. Therefore, for solving this problem the IEEE 802.11 wireless network protocols and cellular communication standards (both GSM and CDMA) use Viterbi algorithm, which envisages a significant reduction in the space of studied code vectors.

The algorithm performs the sequential decoding of the set r with the elimination of the solutions that cannot be the prefixes to the code word v with the smallest Hamming distance $d_H(r, v)$. In the trellis of the convolutional code of the memory m , such process is represented by a search of the optimal route with the limitation of the subpaths number on each level of the graph to 2^m .

We shall discuss the example of the algorithm execution for the information message $v = \langle 11 \ 01 \ 10 \ 01 \rangle$, terminated by the tail $\langle 11 \ 00 \rangle$ and distorted in the channel to the form $r = \langle 10 \ 01 \ 10 \ 01 \ 01 \ 00 \rangle$. In this case, the coding device is given by the graph from Figure 3, and the trellis diagram of the generated message is contained in Figure 10(a).

By implementing an iterative search of the optimal code word (Figure 10(b)), the Viterbi algorithm generates a set of paths v with the calculated values of the Hamming metrics $d_H(r, v)$. On each subsequent step, the algorithm finds the next node for every path and updates the values of their metrics. On the level σ_3 , the Viterbi algorithm reduces by half the number of possible routes by selecting for each graph state a single precursor with the lowest value d_H . Thus, the formation of the

optimal solution requires the study of only 4 paths on each stage of the decoding process [15, 16].

(a)

(b)

Figure 10. Example of the information message decoding by means of the Viterbi algorithm

The result code vector is highlighted in the trellis diagram in Figure 10(a). During the decoding procedure, two random errors have been corrected, and as a consequence, the receiver has fully recovered the contents of the original message generated by the transmitter. This correction capability is determined by the free distance of the convolutional code $d_{free} = 5$.

However, the major drawback of the Viterbi algorithm is a significant number of the metric values calculated for each node in the trellis chart and the large space of memory required to their storage. As a result, the usage of this algorithm for the high values of the code restriction and the large coding window width is limited.

Therefore, a number of other methods for effective recovery of the convolutional codes is suggested. For example, the stack algorithm [17] works with several paths arranging them by the calculated values of metrics. On each step, the route located in the top of the stack is branched, and the 2^d new paths are formed. Instead, the routes with the worst values of the metrics are displaced from the end of the stack. This method has a much lower space complexity than the Viterbi algorithm, but its major drawback is the stack sorting at each computation step.

Fano algorithm at each stage of the decoding process retains the information regarding only three paths: the current solution, the previous path and one of the successor routes. Based on this information, it is possible to make the transition between the different paths in the graph. The search process is directed by introducing a dynamic threshold that enables to detect the erroneous routes and avoid them by returning to the previous branches. Compared to the Viterbi algorithm, the time of this method execution is greater, but it requires a much smaller memory space, and therefore, is widely used for the processing of the vectors with the high values of the code restriction m [18].

Table 3 shows the distribution of the best known convolutional decoding algorithms between the strategies used to search the code sequences v . Based on the study results given in work [16], the complexity of the methods that do not use the sorting procedure is much lower, and the most efficient are the algorithms that search the vectors in the width and depth. By generalizing these observations, we

Table 3. The main search approaches of some convolutional decoding algorithms

The code word search strategies	Metric-first	Breadth-first	Depth-first
With sorting	Stack algorithm, merge algorithm, bucket algorithm	M-algorithm	–
Without sorting	–	Viterbi algorithm, Simmons-Wittke algorithm	Fano algorithm

can clearly outline the trends of the decoding algorithms development.

Conclusion

The modern IEEE 802.11 wireless networks use the methods of block and convolutional coding of information, represented by the complementary codes CCK and PBCC technology respectively. The convolutional coding is efficiently applied in the channels with the additive white noise and random distribution of errors. Therefore, its usage in the wireless network protocols is a key factor in increasing their resistance to the external interference.

However, a large potential of the convolutional coding remains unfulfilled due to the absence of the efficient methods of the received signal restoration. The capacities of the current algorithms are limited to decoding the short messages with the low code restriction, resulting in the loss of the corrective properties. Consequently, the development of the new high-speed systems requires the improvement of the modern methods of the signal decoding. In particular, the implementation of the decoders equipped with the artificial intelligence systems used to restore the corrupted vectors is now extremely promising.

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Authors

Artem V. Potebnia — the 1st year master, Faculty of Radiophysics, Electronics and Computer Systems, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Kyiv, Ukraine; E-mail: poteba@yandex.ru

Sergiy D. Pogorilyy — Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor, Department of Computer Engineering, Faculty of Radiophysics, Electronics and Computer Systems, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Kyiv, Ukraine; E-mail: sdp@univ.net.ua